

ABSTRACTS

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P3-66 Gaseous Ozone to Improve the Microbial Safety of Spices and Nuts

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Introduction: An increase in reported outbreaks associated with low-moisture foods (LMFs) highlights a need to investigate non-thermal gaseous technologies to increase the safety of spices and nuts without compromising product quality.

Purpose: The objective of this study was to inactivate *Salmonella* spp. in different spices and nuts using gaseous ozone treatments and evaluate the suitability of *Enterococcus faecium* as a potential surrogate.

Methods: Four food products (basil leaves, black peppercorn, chia seeds, and walnuts) were inoculated with cocktails of *Salmonella* spp. and *E. faecium* and equilibrated to water activity (a_w) of 0.55. Two-gram samples of inoculated foods were treated in a customized chamber with ozone concentrations of 900-930 ppm at relative humidity (RH) of 70-90% for time intervals of 1-5 h, followed by mild heating at 40°C /4h. Means from 3 batches were compared with JMP Pro (significance level of 5%). Survival data were used to fit 2 primary models (Log-Linear and Weibull) to evaluate the goodness of fit.

Results: At ozone concentration of 900-930 ppm and RH of 90%, the 5 h ozone treatment resulted in maximum log CFU/g reductions of 5.0±0.4 for basil, 2.5±0.2 for black pepper, 1.5±0.2 for walnuts, and 1.1±0.1 for chia seeds. There were no significant differences between 1 and 5 h ozone treatments for chia seeds or walnuts ($P < 0.05$). Post-treatment mild heating at 40°C for 4 h further inactivated *Salmonella* by 1-1.5 log CFU/g for black pepper and basil. *E. faecium* was a good surrogate for *Salmonella* in basil leaves. Based on lower R^2 and RMSE values, the Weibull model provided better goodness of fit for all products.

Significance: Results of this study indicate some synergistic effects of ozone, relative humidity, and mild heating treatments to improve the microbial safety of spices and nuts during storage, though the food matrix may be a limiting factor.

P3-67 UV-C Inactivation of *Clostridium Botulinum* type B Strain in Opaque Coconut Water

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Introduction: *Clostridium botulinum* spores pose a hazard in low acid beverages (coconut water). Application of non-thermal technologies such as UV-C irradiation to inactivate endospores in foods requires an understanding of its UV sensitivities.

Purpose: To evaluate the ability of UV-C light to inactivate dormant endospores of *C. botulinum* in coconut water.

Methods: The spores of non-proteolytic strain Type B (TJ980B) of *C. botulinum* were used for this study. The toxin serotype of *C. botulinum* spore crop was verified using the DIGoxigenin-labeled Enzyme-Linked-Immunosorbent Assay (DIG-ELISA). Optical properties of CW were measured using a double-beam spectrophotometer. UV-C irradiation was applied to stirred samples of coconut water (3mL, optical depth=0.9 mm), using a collimated beam system operating at 253.7 nm wavelength. A series of known UV doses (0 - 32 mJ.cm⁻²) were delivered to spore suspension of coconut water (N=3). After treatment, the samples were heat shocked for spore's activation. Enumeration of spores was performed by serial dilution plate count method.

Results: Populations of *C. botulinum* dormant spores were reduced by ~ 3 log at the UV-C dosage of 32 mJ.cm⁻². The inactivation kinetics of spores were fitted to a log-linear model with k_{max} value of 0.24 ± 0.02 1/mJ.cm⁻² and D_{10} value of 9.41 mJ.cm⁻²/log. Furthermore, ELISA results showed that there is no toxin production at UV dose of 32 mJ.cm⁻².

Significance: The calculated D_{10} values will be useful to estimate the target doses required for five-log reduction of *C. botulinum* in low acidic beverages by UV-C irradiation. Further proliferation of the technology will include conducting extensive pilot studies using a continuous flow UV system.

P3-68 Microwave Pasteurization of Ready Meals

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Introduction: The pasteurization by microwaves is a process which treats quickly, prolongs the shelf life of food and minimizes the deterioration of quality compared to the conventional heating. The microwave treatment, heats directly by absorption of electromagnetic energy by the food components. This process allows an electrification of the processes.

Purpose: Show that microwave can pasteurize with better organoleptic properties.

Methods: A continuous microwave unit, was installed at CTCPA (France). The equipment consists of 24 kW microwave power - 2450 MHz - Length 5 m. An autoclave treatment versus a microwave treatment with the same pasteurization value (3000 min) will be compared. The recipe is pasta with vegetables and salmon, sweet potato puree, and green beans. 100 selected consumers will taste the two recipes and will have to evaluate the following criteria: colors, texture, taste, and overall appreciation. The tastings are organized in individual booths, in compliance with the NFV09-105 standard: the service of the cooked dishes is done according to the monadic sequential mode following a Latin square plan. The energy consumption was measured by used a EnergiMeter: Fluke 434.

Results: The results are better on all the criteria for the microwave modality, and they are significantly different (student test 5%) for the following modalities: general appreciation (7.2 vs. 6.66), color of the salmon (6.3 vs. 5.36), color of the sweet potato puree (7.79 vs. 7.66), texture of the salmon (6.05 vs. 5.3), taste of the dish (7.03 vs. 6.35). The intentions of consumption are very significantly favorable for microwave 74 vs 57 % (Chi² test significant 0.1%). Concerning the energy consumption, we go from 0.610 to 0.362 kWh/ kg of product respectively for autoclave and microwave.

Significance: The process is advantageous due to its volumetric heating principle. It can pasteurize without compromise the organoleptic properties by consuming less energy and is electrical processing.

P3-69 Minimize Post-Harvest Loss in Stored Grains by Microwaves

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Introduction: During storage, grains can be infested by insects with negative impact on its quality as well as losses. Global crop losses is between 11-14% according to previously studies.

Purpose: Show that microwave can be an efficient process for the destruction of insects.

Methods: A continuous microwave unit was installed at RISE (Sweden). The equipment consists of 54 kW microwave power - 915 MHz; product flow 3 tons of grains/hour. Grain weevils were selected for this study since it is common in infested grains and one of the more resistant species. The grains with insects (cultivated) were kept for at least 3 weeks in order to establish a collection with all differential stages, eggs, larvae, pupa and fully developed. The grains were put in sealed polyester bags and randomly mixed and for each target temperature. After, microwave bags were collected and opened to count the number of viable and dead insects, respectively. The remaining grains were transferred into the incubator. Emerging insects were counted every 2-3 days, by use of a stereo microscope, for a period of 6 weeks.

Results: We could notice a strong heat-dependent mortality after treating the insects with temperatures ranging from 50°C to 60°C. However, at higher temperatures, the mortality was higher, with heat treatment at 70°C at 8.4 seconds exposure time is sufficient to obtain up to 100% mortality (significant 5%). Concerning the germination, the values are very close to the control (92 vs 95 %). Concerning the baking properties, the following analyses were per-

dients' components as independent variables to predict whether a recipe was TCS or non-TCS. Recipe text mining was also performed. Data analysis was performed using the R statistical computing language version 4.2.2 and the R Tidyverse libraries version 1.3.1.

Results: Salt, sugar, and water content create a weak linear regression model of water activity ($R^2 = 0.53$). The best logistic model for predicting TCS had a training accuracy of 69.5% using the components of fats ($p=0.05$), sugars ($p=0.02$), and water ($p=0.002$). The specificity of the model (true negative rate) was 0.74, and the sensitivity (true positive rate) was 0.56. A pruned decision tree classifier split on starch and sugars, had a training accuracy of 0.8, specificity of 0.95, and sensitivity of 0.5. The application of heat (43 recipes) did not significantly impact the model, possibly due to the variability in baking times and temperatures, and text mining of recipes was unsuccessful.

Significance: The ability to predict TCS status based on baked food ingredients and recipes could aid cottage food producers and state health departments. The results here are promising but require further refinement.

P3-135 Comparison of Multiple Pathogen Growth Models Using Real World Transport Data for Leafy Greens

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Introduction: Many mathematical models are available for predicting pathogen growth in foods, including specialized models for foods like leafy greens. There has been a little systematic comparison of these multiple models to determine their suitability and differences in prediction.

Purpose: We compared multiple mathematical models of *Salmonella* spp., *Escherichia coli* and *Listeria monocytogenes* on leafy greens to determine prediction differences when real-world temperature data are used.

Methods: Temperature data were obtained from sixteen shipments that were monitored in 5-minute increments for transit temperature from June 2010 to May 2011. Relevant growth models were selected from the literature for *Salmonella* (n=6), *E. coli* O157:H7 (n=6), and *L. monocytogenes* (n=4). Data analysis was performed using the R statistical computing language version 4.2.2 and the specialized R Tidyverse libraries version 1.3.1.

Results: The *Salmonella* predictions from the Gibson and Puerta-Gomez models predict the least growth and were not statistically different from each other. The Mishra and Sant'Ana *Salmonella* models predict the most growth and were not significantly different from one another. Two other models (Veys and Koseki) were intermediary. The *Salmonella* model Kendall W effect size was 0.95, which indicates the risk ranking of shipments was consistent across *Salmonella* models. The Puerta-Gomez *E. coli* model predicted less growth than the other five models, and the Buchanan, McKellar, and Veys models predict more growth than the other models. The *E. coli* Kendall W effect size was 0.95, which indicates the choice of *E. coli* model does not appreciably alter the risk ranking of shipments. The *L. monocytogenes* models from Mishra Sant'Ana, Koseki, and Buchanan are also significantly different, with a Kendall W effect size of 0.97.

Significance: While model predictions were different, high Kendall W effect sizes indicate that model choice has minimal impact on risk management once a risk tolerance is set.

P3-136 Modeling the Combination Effects of Temperature, pH, Water Activity, Nitrite, and Organic Acids on the Growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* in Processed Meat Products

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Introduction: Delicatessen meats are reported to be the leading vehicle of foodborne *listeriosis* outbreaks with a high fatality. Predictive models are valuable tools to assess and manage public health risks.

Purpose: The objective of this study was to develop and validate a global model based on food matrices' literature data for predicting the growth of *Listeria monocytogenes* in processed meat products.

Methods: The model considers the effect of seven environmental parameters including temperature, pH, water activity, nitrite, acetate, lactate, and propionate with and without interaction effects. Experimental growth curves of *Listeria* in food matrices (beef, pork, and poultry) were collected from ComBase, or modeled from research publications, and analyzed, after which a total of 414 growth curves were retained. The four-parameter logistic model with delay was used as the primary model to estimate the growth parameters (N_0 , N_{max} , t_{lag} , μ_{max}) for each curve.

Results: The growth rate data were divided into two sets, about 355 data were used to build the model, and 135 food matrix datasets for validation. A gamma concept-based bespoke model was developed and performance was evaluated using bias factor (Bf), accuracy factor (Af), and acceptable simulation zone (ASZ) of $\pm 0.5 \log \text{ cfu/unit}$. The developed global model had an acceptable Bf of 1.02, Af of 1.17, and ASZ score was more than 72%. Therefore, the gamma secondary model developed using food matrix data provided a valid prediction for the growth of *Listeria* in processed meat products.

Significance: This study is the first to develop a model that considers nitrite, propionate, acetate, and lactate as combined inhibitors of *Listeria*, along with temperature, pH, and water activity. The results of our study provide significant insights into the need for the development and validation of predictive models in real food matrices rather than laboratory media alone. The model may be useful in timely decision-making and quantitative risk assessment in RTE-cooked meat products.

P3-137 Estimation of *Listeria monocytogenes* Levels within Apple Production Environments Utilizing Reverse Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment

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Introduction: A 2014 outbreak from consumption of caramel apples contaminated with *Listeria monocytogenes* highlights a current gap with modern food microbial detection technology limits and *L. monocytogenes* contamination levels.

Purpose: As the 2014 outbreak proves, *Listeria monocytogenes* prevalence becoming ubiquitous within produce environments accentuates the need to investigate concentration levels of the pathogen within the handling facilities.

Methods: This study uses Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment (QMRA) to analyze a Listeriosis outbreak from 2014 associated with contaminated caramel apples. QMRA is a modeling framework that commonly uses environmental sampling data to characterize pathogen fate, transport, and the likelihood of adverse health effects. However, in reverse, epidemiological study results from the outbreak can be used to estimate pathogenic levels. To capture human variability, two models were constructed (average-adult & pregnant women-stillbirths) with four consumer handling scenarios based on storage temperature (7 °C, 25 °C) and storage duration (1 day, 1 week). 1000 iterations of Monte Carlo simulations were conducted to supply a resultant distribution of *Listeria monocytogenes* estimates to better minimize uncertainty associated with each model.

Results: The average adult model's scenarios of room temperature short & extended and cold storage short & extended estimated mean values of 0.147, 0.0713, 0.198, and 0.0754 Colony Forming Units per gram (CFU/g), respectively, in comparison to the stillbirth model's results of the scenarios that provided mean values of 1.24, 0.601, 1.67, and 0.635 CFU/g, respectively, demonstrate a very low-level prevalence of the pathogen within these environments. Spearman rho correlation estimates determined the most uncertainty for both average adult and stillbirths lies in the growth parameter for 75% of the consumer handling practice scenarios except short term cold storage.

Significance: The findings from the reverse QMRA will be used to inform policymakers and food science technology about the limitations of current detection methods utilized for low-concentration pathogens, such as *L. monocytogenes*.